

Research-in-Progress Paper

The Montado Living Lab: Catalysing soil health through formal and informal co-construction networks

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Abstract

The Montado, a complex farming system, faces significant threats from global pressures pushing towards either agricultural intensification or land abandonment, despite its crucial role in delivering high-quality production alongside diverse ecosystem services.

We introduce the *Montado Living Lab* - Montado LL (Filipe et al, 2025), a Living Lab centered on the Portuguese agro-silvo-pastoral system Montado, and the *Tertúlia's do Montado* (Guimarães et al, 2024), a transdisciplinary dialogue platform that aim to collectively frame the sustainability problems of the Montado for better alignment of research and practice through the integration of shared knowledge into real-world context.

This study analyses how the formal structure and collaborative approach of the *Montado LL* and the informal structure of *Tertúlias do Montado* facilitate the generation of context-specific knowledge, testing and validation of innovations, overall driving processes for the adoption of sustainable soil and other management practices and, the production of evidence-based knowledge to inform, adapt and develop policies.

Key words

Agro-silvo-pastoral, Montado, Soil Health, Sustainable Management, Transdisciplinarity, Public Policies

Introduction

The Montado, a southern Portuguese distinct agroforestry system spanning approximately one million hectares, is a unique landscape with high economical, ecological and social relevance, characterised by its ecological richness, and climate change resilience. These features are mostly linked with the combination of a mosaic landscape, that includes cork oak and cork oak forests, pockets of natural shrubs, grazing livestock, and occasionally diverse farming practices (Pinto-Correia et al, 2001). Such variety is both an advantage and a challenge, which requires intricate agrosilvo pastoral and cattle management skills and integration of diverse knowledge types.

Since the 90's the Montado is facing significant challenges mostly associated with climate change, soil degradation and tree density decline. This has both economic and ecological negative consequences which urge the development of solutions tailored to the Montado's diverse areas and contexts. The complexity of the Montado, with its interwoven components and the need to integrate diverse knowledge, undoubtedly makes finding these solutions difficult. Identifying and pinpointing the most critical areas for intervention and research, exploring the economic pressures on producers, the impacts of specific climate change effects in the region, understanding and addressing the socio-economic factors driving land abandonment and reflecting on necessary policy adjustments to address the essential issues from Montado, require more than typical research and development approaches.

Methodological approach

Departing from the concept of transdisciplinary research (Klein et al, 2001) and aiming to use this methodology towards the development of solutions to Montado's decline, two different approaches have been developed which involve collaborative work with various academic disciplines, as well as other non-academic practitioners from private and public administration sectors, associations and other stakeholders with links to Montado. These initiatives are the *Montado Living Lab* (Montado LL), a dedicated Living Lab focused on the Portuguese Montado agroforestry system, and the *Tertúlias do Montado*, a transdisciplinary dialogue platform, both using collaborative approaches to strengthen the system's sustainability and resilience.

The *Montado LL*, is an ENoLL Living Lab, comprising 40 diverse stakeholders including farmers, researchers, policymakers, associations and companies, which serves as a real-

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world experimentation and co-construction innovation hub and that fosters research production and knowledge dissemination in close collaboration between science and practice, with questions identified and formulated jointly between multiple partners and addressed by researchers from different disciplinary backgrounds. The *Montado LL* accounts for the participation of 20 farmers, that make available at least 2 experimental plots each and which enable applied research in real world contexts and over periods of time longer than those applied in typical research projects (5 to 10 years).

The *Tertulia's do Montado*, is an open and structured co-construction space, functioning since 2016 with more than 50 in door, outdoor and online sessions, each averaging 30 participants of the typologies numerated before (Guimarães et al, 2016). The *Tertúlias do Montado* serves as a long-term transdisciplinary dialogue platform addressing the contemporary decline of the Montado agro-silvo-pastoral system.

The use of co-construction and transdisciplinary approaches is common within both initiatives, and is integrated in several co-creation workshops, for discussion of key topics of relevance within the Montado.

A key difference between the two initiatives lies in participant involvement. The *Montado LL* has a closed membership of forty individuals, while *Tertúlias do Montado* welcomes anyone interested in the discussion topics, potentially leading to a larger and more diverse group of participants.

Furthermore, the fundamental missions and objectives of *Montado LL* and *Tertúlias do Montado* diverge significantly. For the *Tertúlias do Montado* the main mission is to “foster the exchange and valuing of different types of knowledge, promote critical thinking, inspire new questions, and encourage the search for new knowledge” focusing on Montado related questions. The five objectives to be achieved within the *Tertúlias do Montado* are i) build a shared understanding of the issue under discussion; ii) ensure analysis and debate are broad, not limited to a single perspective; iii) promote agile, constructive interaction among participants with diverse viewpoints; iv) connect scientific knowledge with practical and empirical experience; v) encourage participants to apply the knowledge gained in real-life contexts.

The *Montado Living Lab* mission is the development, testing, and promotion of sustainable practices to enhance soil health, restore tree cover, and foster ecological and socio-economic balance in Montado. The vision is to build capacities and tailored solutions using co-construction approaches, involving input from multiple stakeholders

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with relevance for the Montado system, namely Academia, Associations, Public Administration and Companies with activities linked with the Montado. Key deliverables and objectives from the *Montado Living Lab* include: i) long lasting partnership ruled by trust and transparency; ii) regenerative practices grounded on the soil health; iii) evidence of their impact, on productivity, biodiversity, tree regeneration and water retention; iv) biodiversity / ecosystem services / carbon accounting for different Montado types and management typologies; v) criteria and indicators to monitor multiple environmental results (carbon sequestration, soil quality, farmland biodiversity, tree renewal); vi) training and capacity building for producers, managers and professionals, on integrated and adaptive management; vii) monitoring and assessment of the impact of present and planned public policies; viii) institutional arrangements and governance models adapted to Montado multifunctionality and climate change.

Results

The *Tertúlias do Montado*, has served as a vital dialogue platform for different actors engaged in the Montado and has aimed to bridge the gap between scientific and practical knowledge. Through social exchange, mutual understanding and trust, the *Tertúlias do Montado* has fostered critical thinking through informal online and presential exchange among researchers, landowners, managers, public institution staff, and anyone connected to the Montado. Since its inception (2016), 43 *Tertúlias do Montado* events took place, of different natures and involving diverse number of actors and thematics, spanning from training, discussion moments on key Montado aspects, school visits, visits to Montado farms, etc.

Within *Tertúlias do Montado*, participants collectively create a common agenda of issues to discuss. Each session, which typically lasts three hours, is planned and facilitated with guiding questions and small group activities to encourage participation. The group decides on the next topic before the end of each meeting. Sessions can be held indoors or outdoors, and some topics may require more than one session. The facilitator structures the session based on participant suggestions, and feedback is collected in person or through an anonymous questionnaire. Each meeting is recorded to create a follow-up report that summarizes the main points and any unresolved questions. A [blog](#), which archives all published reports, and a WhatsApp group comprising over 100 members function as primary channels for communication and knowledge dissemination.

Established in January 2024 and sharing some members with *Tertúlias do Montado*, the *Montado LL* has primarily concentrated on defining its governance, operational models

and communication strategies and gathering key information about anticipated expectations and challenges to be addressed. Leveraging workshops and surveys, Living Lab members identified and prioritized key practices for each stage of its innovation cycle, from initial ideas to solution implementation (figure 1). Notably, co-mapping and co-creation emerged as priority tools for fostering innovation. This preference likely stems from the positive experiences gained through years of employing transdisciplinary and co-construction methods within the *Tertúlias do Montado*.

Practices within Innovation Cycle

Figure 1. Top 3 – Preferred practices within the Innovation Cycle

The surveys also sought to identify the crucial infrastructures for developing solutions for the Montado (figure 2). Experimental farms, laboratories, and knowledge-sharing databases and platforms were deemed more important than co-creation infrastructures, software, and digital tools. Software and hardware for data acquisition and analysis, task management and prioritization software, and other co-creation tools, were considered less relevant.

The Montado Living Lab has chosen at least two experimental plots from each of its 21 farms. A standardized method for collecting and testing soil samples has been implemented across all these plots. These samples will be analysed for their physical, chemical, and biological properties to create a baseline of soil health. Vegetation assessments and remote sensing were in addition used. All data is being stored on a central database, making it easy to share information and knowledge.

Living Lab Infrastructures

Figure 2. Top 3 – Most relevant Living Lab Infrastructures

Montado LL members also prioritized Montado's challenges (figure 3), which then informed the identification of training and capacity-building needs, as well as key research topics aimed at bridging the research-production gap. The top three critical issues identified were the lack of specific financial and legal policy instruments for Montado, high levels of soil degradation, and the impacts of climate change and inadequate soil management. While also acknowledged as relevant, other challenges such as biodiversity loss and degradation, declining tree cover and growth, water scarcity, and issues related to soil health mapping (including soil sampling and characterization tools) were assigned lower priority in the initial survey assessment.

A key priority within the LL is the need to create and/or update policies, informed by research findings, that promote soil health and sustainable Montado management practices. This is a complex issue that requires a balanced approach involving multiple stakeholders. The process should incorporate the practical needs of farmers, technical data from academic research (such as monitoring the impact of new policies on soil health), and the policy-making expertise of public administration and government authorities. Solution demonstration, piloting, and transfer to external stakeholders were considered less relevant at this early stage of the *Montado LL*'s development. Recognizing the absence of specific policies for the soil health improvement in agriculture, forestry and Montado, some stakeholders from the *Montado Living Lab* collaborated with PlanAPP, a public administration entity focused on policy development. The project – Soil and Water 2030 goal was to create a methodological approach to establish soil regeneration objectives. Through workshops and interviews, it was found that existing policies for soil regeneration, often fail to meet the specific needs of local areas, are not implemented or monitored effectively, and are not well-coordinated with each other. This

analysis led to a set of recommendations for revising these policies. These recommendations were compiled into a Policy Brief, which will be used by various government bodies—including the Secretary-General of the Government (SG-Gov), the National office for Planning, Policies, and General Administration (GPP), and the Directorate-General for Territory (DGT)—to guide the creation and adaptation of future policies.

Some members of the *Montado Living Lab* are also testing the *Results-Based Montado Management* initiative, a pilot measure under the Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy (PEPAC), developed by the MED/University of Évora, which has emerged within the *Tertúlias do Montado* (Guimarães et al, 2019). This project, active in specific municipalities, funds environmental outcomes instead of specific management practices. Landowners have the freedom to choose their own methods, and they receive a five-year contract with payments based on the improvements and environmental results achieved in their Montado plots.

Main challenges within Montado

Figure 3. Top 3 – Main challenges within the Montado

Based on feedback from surveys, workshops, and discussions with stakeholders, several successful funding applications were submitted at both national and European levels. These proposals focused on developing new methods to improve soil health in Montado systems, often using a collaborative, "Living Lab" approach.

Additionally, training programs were created to address key Montado topics. These programs combined classroom learning with practical, hands-on training covering subjects like cork harvesting, cattle management, and soil sampling and analysis.

Tertúlias do Montado and Montado Living Lab – two complementary platforms

As previously mentioned, *Tertúlias do Montado* fosters dialogue, knowledge exchange, and a shared understanding of the Montado's challenges, laying a crucial foundation of trust and collaboration among stakeholders. This groundwork was essential for establishing the Living Lab and remains vital for its effective operation. Knowledge, discussions and insights generated in *Tertúlias do Montado* serve as the bedrock, and basis for R&I activities of the *Montado LL*, guaranteeing that research is rooted in stakeholders' real-world experiences and needs. Conversely, *Montado LL*, with its emphasis on experimentation and solution testing, can provide evidence-based results for sharing and discussion within the *Tertúlias do Montado* platform. This reciprocal exchange enriches the dialogue, promotes the adoption of sustainable practices, and provides a structured approach to rigorously test and validate the practical knowledge emerging from *Tertúlias do Montado* discussions. Furthermore, the evidence-based outcomes from *Montado LL* can inform policy development, leading to more effective and targeted interventions, while the dialogue and knowledge sharing facilitated by *Tertúlias do Montado* ensure that policies align with the Montado community's needs and priorities.

In essence, *Tertúlias do Montado* fosters the social interaction and knowledge exchange necessary to identify key issues and build a shared vision, while the *Montado LL* provides a structured framework for research, innovation, and the development of practical solutions.

Common challenges from both initiatives are linked with participation rate and acceptance of transdisciplinary approaches as a methodology to address the challenges of Montado. A survey undertaken within the *Tertúlias do Montado* platform revealed that some interviewees valued the incorporation of different types of knowledge, while others, mainly older male participants from the research community, emphasized the importance of distinguishing between scientific and empirical knowledge. These points suggest challenges in engaging all stakeholders and achieving full adoption of the transdisciplinary approach, including sustaining the involvement of diverse societal actors, encouraging reflection on contextual assumptions, aligning activities with goals and encourage openness to new perspectives (Isidoro et al, 2025).

Ultimately, this research contributed to understand the role and complementarity of formal and informal governance structures, on co-creation environments, overall driving

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processes for the adoption of sustainable soil and other management practices and, the production of evidence-based knowledge to inform, adapt and develop adapted policies.

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